

MAIN APHROPHORIDAE (HEMIPTERA) VECTORS OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA PAUCA ST53 JUVENILE QUANTITATIVE SAMPLING

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Collecting quantitative population data of *Xylella fastidiosa pauca* ST53 vectors is the primary step in planning control strategies to manage the pathogen invasion in olive orchards. The species, number, and phenology of vectors are crucial to identify, choose, and integrate effective control actions in key-points. Here, we focus on a juvenile quantitative sampling method needed to quantify the control intensity of second key-point of vectors management: the preimaginal vector IPM. In a first approach we collected Aphrophoridae juveniles living on olive orchards herbs framed in a 0,25 m x 1 m transects (Sub-Sampling Unit - SSU - 1/4 m²: 2.500 cm²). Later the herbs were scored in the laboratory by stereomicroscopes and juveniles stored in EtOH 75% for subsequent study. One-year long dataset scrutiny revealed truncated population data at the beginning and the end of the sampling season. Consequently, we elaborated an innovative sequential rinsing sampling technique called AquaSamPling (ASP) by a biomimetic approach to gather data of better quality and to suggest a sampling modality available for the field technician and stakeholders. ASP consists of washing the collected plants several times with a saline solution (0,9% sodium chloride in tap water) to dissolve the insects-froth and force the insects to float in the liquid. The rinsing solution is filtered through a non-woven piece of fabric and used for re-rinse the same herbs batch until filters collect any further juvenile. The rinsing is gentle enough to keep the insects alive, intact and ready to be breed or preserved in EtOH 75%, for counting and identifying. One-year long ASP gathered dataset revealed expected population increase and decreased at the beginning and the end of the sampling season, also allowing to collect eggs in full winter, and to scrutiny eggs development and hatching later in January and February, giving us the ability to forecast new-born presence in the field. ASP has a feasible and essential approach and bypasses the need of a laboratory, making stakeholder able to detail timely and accurately the vector population size and phenology at a fraction of efforts due with a conventional technique.

We further experimented ASP resolving power by subdividing the SSU in six SSSU (Sub-Sub-Sampling Units: 5 x 400 cm² + 1 x 500 = 2.500 cm²) to wash them separately and then rejoined in a single 2.500 cm² SSU. Counting the total of collected juveniles revealed that five 20 x 20 (400 cm²: 2.000 cm²) SSSU work better than a single 2.500 cm² SSU. Overall field ASP for vector control suggests sampling the densest and aged herbs belonging preferably to Asteraceae, Apiaceae, Rubiaceae and Primulaceae in the orchard, to get the highest vectors to count and the most advanced phenology of vectors.

This "worst case" sampling helps to better trigger the juvenile vector control actions intensity in correspondence with the observed population field peak at the pass from last naïad to first nymph.

